

Clivia nobilis

Green-tip forest lily

© A. de Wet Steyn

Group: Monocot

Size: 30 to 80 cm in height

Distribution:

Clivia nobilis is endemic to the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. Colonies are concentrated towards the coast, from just north of the Sundays River Mouth, extending up along the coast to the Mbashe River area. Although mostly found among dune vegetation, some colonies occur as far inland as the vicinity of Makhanda (previously Grahamstown).

Importance:

Green-tip forest lily was the first species of *Clivia* to be formally described. Specimens were sent to Europe for domestication as early as 1830, playing an important role in the domestication of *Clivia* as an ornamental plant. Illegal poaching for the international rare plant market has led to a decline of this species in nature. Additionally, this *Clivia* is collected and used in the traditional medicine market. Its unique chemical (alkaloid) properties have also made it a subject of international scientific study.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 380.32 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 11.68 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 16.44 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.3% [Single: 72.7%, Duplicated: 26.6%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 4 442.77 kilobases

Contig number: 19 823

Sample Contributor contact details:

Felix Middleton

Clivia Society of South Africa

felix.middleton@limagrain.com